

Leadership of a Company MERCADONA

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 01 April 2022	The company Mercadona was chosen for this work, as it is an innovative organization marked by its recent internationalization. We carry out the characterization of the company, referring to its mission, vision and values. Next, we will present the organization chart of the company that shows how it is divided in terms of management levels and their respective competencies. Subsequently, we made a brief description of the leader, showing some aspects of his journey to the present and relating these characteristics to the subject under study (social responsibility, corporate governance, etc.) and to his leadership style. Furthermore, we analyze the strategy present at Mercadona, addressing the topics taught in the curricular unit concerning competitive advantage and competitive systems.
Corresponding Author: Vaz, Angela	In short, we intend to conclude about the type of leadership that Juan Roig chooses to obtain adherence and success in his company.
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1. COMPANY PRESENTATION

Mercadona is a family-owned company founded in 1977 within the Cárnicas Roig group. However, in 1981, Juan Roig takes over the management of the company with the help of his wife, Hortensia Herrero, thus starting an independent company, with the majority shareholders (80% of the capital).

Over time, the company has progressively evolved based on its own management model, which has been applied since 1993: the Total Quality Model. Mercadona is one of the leading physical and online supermarket companies in the food distribution sector in Spain and recently in Portugal.

The organization under analysis is made up of 85,800 employees, 300 of which are in Portugal. In addition, all workers undergo specific training in order to obtain skills to offer maximum service excellence.

Finally, the company works together and in the long term with its suppliers in order to satisfy the needs of its customers.

Total Quality Model

As mentioned above, Mercadona has its own business model that helps employees in decision-making and in the development of various appropriate strategies to meet their objectives.

According to the picture on the side, we can see that through this model the company is able to satisfy with the same intensity the five components of the Sustainable Agrifood chain:

- “The Boss” (customers)
- The Contributor
- The provider
- The society
- The capital

1.1. The mission

“Fill the Belly”

The company aims to provide consumers with products that meet their basic needs such as eating, drinking, personal care, home care and animal care. In addition, it seeks to guarantee low prices, maximum quality and food safety.

“O Chefe” no centro de todas as decisões

1.2. The vision

The company's main objective is to be an organization that is dedicated to satisfying the needs of customers (“the boss”) and of which they are proud. In addition, it aims to achieve a sustainable agri-food chain.

1.3. Values

- o Stability
- o Equality
- o training and promotion
- o Conciliation
- o Retribution

1.4. Chart

An organizational chart is a method of structuring teams within a company. The purpose of this tool is to organize the spaces in which each professional will be inserted. It must be part of an organization's strategic

planning, as it is through it that the relationships of responsibilities become evident.

An organizational chart is created with boxes that each contain the existing positions in the corporation, such as CEO, vice president, director, manager, assistant, intern, among others. Lines connect the boxes to demonstrate hierarchies.

A tool like this offers a panoramic view of the organization and is interesting not only for managers, but also for collaborators at all levels.

Mercadona is undoubtedly one of the largest entities in Spain, in fact, it has a very good position worldwide. In view of this, the analysis of Mercadona's organizational chart is recommended for Spanish or Hispanic entrepreneurs.

In the case of Mercadona, we can see that we have a pyramidal structure, where at the top are institutional-level managers (Juan Roig), which is important for developing strategies and for making long-term decisions.

Then we can see several managers who guide the

workers and are guided by higher level managers, called middle managers. Such managers present themselves as managers of different divisions and specific functions such as, for example, human resources, finance, IT, etc. These are necessary for making short-term decisions.

Finally, in blue we see the base of the pyramid referring to operational managers. These are in charge of routines and procedures related to the technical component.

Essential competencies of a manager:

Having presented the various levels of management, we can see that they have different importance in relation to the three essential skills of a manager:

- Conceptual
- technique
- Human relations

In this way, regarding the institutional level, we can see that it has more characteristics related to conceptual aptitude, since it needs to see the organization as a whole, in order to assimilate abstract ideas and apply them in its arduous process of taking decisions.

On the other hand, at the operational level, they need a capacity more related to the application of knowledge in the execution of the work, which is the technical aptitude.

Finally, human relationships remain constant throughout the pyramid, since the ability to communicate, understand, motivate and obtain buy-in from other people is a necessary and inherent ability at all levels of management.

2. LEADER PROFILE PRESENTATION

Juan Roig was born on October 8, 1949 in Valencia. He married Hortensia Herrero, vice president of the company, having four daughters.

Degree in Economic Sciences from the University of Valencia. In 1975, he joined the Cárnicas Roig business group, owned by his father and, in October 1981, assumes the direction of the company that starts its activity as an independent company.

Juan Roig is also Honorary President of the Spanish Association of Commercial Coding (AECOC), Vice President of the Spanish Association of Self-Services and Supermarkets (ASEDAS) and Honorary President of the School of Entrepreneurs (EDEM).

On a personal level, he supports entrepreneurs through Marina de Empresas, one of the main entrepreneurship hubs in the Mediterranean, and is the driving force behind Lanzadera, a business incubator and accelerator, President of the Trinidad Alfonso Foundation and majority shareholder of Valencia Basket Club.

CONSELHO DE ADMINISTRAÇÃO				
Presidente	Vice-presidente	Secretaria do Conselho	Vogais	
Juan Roig	Hortensia M ^ª Herrero	Carolina Roig		Hortensia Roig Amparo Roig Juana Roig Rafael Gómez Fernando Roig

3. LEADERSHIP AT MERCADONA

“A company needs leadership capable of carrying out all the changes necessary, if not, it will disappear” Juan Roig

The leader of the company in question is concerned with continuing its leadership in the Spanish market and further expanding its business in Portugal. In addition, the leader has increasingly focused on knowing the needs of its customers, adapting to each one of them and always being concerned with bringing them the best products at the best prices.

3.1. Social responsibility

Mercadona's Corporate Social Responsibility policies include numerous projects supported by 3 pillars:

- logistical optimization (transport more with fewer resources),
- energy efficiency (using only the energy needed) and
- waste management (prevention and reintegration of waste as raw material).

As practical applications of these policies, we can highlight the New Efficient Store Model, in which energy consumption was reduced by up to 40% compared to the previous store model, and on the other hand the optimization of truck routes so that they never travel empty – between suppliers, logistics blocks and stores. It is also worth mentioning the donations to institutions and/or food banks, which last year reached 9,600 tons.

3.2. Corporate Governance

Corporate governance can be defined as the system of rules and conduct relating to the exercise of direction and control of companies. Corporate governance expresses a company's relationship with its shareholders and in a broader way the relationship that the company maintains with its stakeholders.

The company, as an open system, influences and is influenced by its external environment. Thus, we assess that all its operations will affect society in general. In other words, the company's objective transcends the profit and turns to value creation. In this way, the scope of the managers' concerns includes the relationships they establish with all the actors in business life.

There are 3 models of corporate governance:

- shareholder model
- stakeholder model
- Intermediate model (enlightened shareholder)

In the case of Mercadona, it adopts the intermediate model since, to be successful, the company must have satisfied customers who want to buy its products and services, motivated employees in their jobs, satisfied suppliers to be its business partners, and “license” to operate and be accepted by the community in which it operates. In this model, the relationship with stakeholders takes into account ethics, the quality of products and services and customer satisfaction, working conditions and employee satisfaction.

4. STRATEGY AT MERCADONA

Competitive advantage has two types of sources: differentiation and costs. Starting with cost, this represents the value that can be reduced in all activities in the value chain. On the other hand, we have differentiation that is obtained in activities related to customers.

In the case of the company under study, the competitive advantage is obtained through differentiation, thus highlighting one of the types of competitive systems: the activities of differentiation. This competitive system is part of the company, since it is dedicated to the production of its own brand products and different from the competition, thus gaining defenses against the entry of new competitors through greater adherence by customers.

In addition, Mercadona also obtains a competitive advantage based on costs, through the practice of low prices on all its products compared to other supermarkets, especially with regard to products from its own brands: Hacendado (Food), Bosque Verde (Home Cleaning), Deliplus (Perfumery and Cosmetics) and Compy (Pet Care). Reference

brands in terms of high quality and innovative products – some of them didn't even exist on the market.

Finally, we can see that the organization recently (2019) adopted the internationalization strategy by opening several stores in Portugal, most of which are concentrated in the north of the country, since Mercadona's intention will initially be to partially conquer the country and later be able to expand the business and thus conquer Portugal as a whole.

5. EGOS MAP

Adriano Freire, president of Instituto Egos and author of the book Mapa Egos believed that our level of self-knowledge is more limited than we imagine, because we are not fully aware of all our personality characteristics.

Thus, he developed the EGOS Map, which has a huge impact on people's lives, as it aims to provide a clearer and more complete vision, helping to discover who they really are and to be able to transform themselves into who they want to be, thus improving their professional and personal lives.

Each person integrates the characteristics of all the EGOS profiles in their own way in their own way. But, due to its biological and psychological nature, it tends to assume the characteristics of certain profiles throughout life.

In specific situations, the person may need to emphasize certain characteristics, thus temporarily adopting personalities more suited to those contexts (adapted personalities).

Map Egos in Mercadona

According to what is expected at the top of the organization, the leader has a governing profile, since he is process-oriented and likes to be rigorous in decision-making and in the choice of workers, thus providing a training of 40 hours per week. in Portugal or Spain, minimizing the risk of error. In this way, the leader proves to be quite logical and reveals his preference for structured environments that he controls.

In addition, the leader also presents characteristics of an entrepreneurial profile, as he is goal-oriented and likes to compete and overcome new challenges, such as integration in the Portuguese food distribution business. Being thus, willing to take risks and face eventual failures.

As usual, the leader presents characteristics of all the Egos Map profiles, although some stand out more than others. However, the profiles that contribute less to the formation of the leader, are equally important for its success.

6. SWOT ANALYSIS

The SWOT analysis is a tool that allows you to make a strategic diagnosis of the company both in the internal environment and in the external environment in which it is located and, thus, it is possible to define future objectives and propose corrections for any problems that the company may be facing.

strengths (Strong points)

- Largest supermarket chain and food distributor in Spain with more than 1300 stores and almost a quarter of the food market share
- It has a good brand value, as it is among the ten most reputable companies in the world
- Strong food delivery channels, including online
- Your products undergo strong quality control checks to ensure freshness and cleanliness.
- The company has a workforce of over 70,000 people

Weaknesses (weaknesses)

- It does not have a strong global presence compared to other leading food retail stores.
- The company has limited brand recognition outside of Spain compared to some other market leaders.

Opportunities

- Customers prefer good quality food in a short time with maximum freshness, so there are many growth opportunities for this industry here
- Opportunity to increase sales by launching new products, optimizing packaging and streamlining your selections.

Threats(Threats)

- Consumers are still not quite ready to buy food online due to the trust factor.
- Increased presence in other international brands

7. CONCLUSION

The elaboration of this work allowed us to make a better analysis of the concepts that were taught during the classes and, above all, allowed us to relate these same concepts with real life, through the chosen company.

Thus, after the elaboration of the work, we can see that Juan Roig chooses a type of leadership marked by differentiation and cost, thus achieving the adhesion of his customers and success in his sales.

This situation can be confirmed by a study by Deco Proteste released at the end of November, which shows that among the 16 brands operating in Portugal, Mercadona stands out especially for the quality of its products.

When carrying out the work, we can also verify through the EGOS map that the leadership presents a mostly governing profile, although some characteristics of the entrepreneurial profile are also observed, thus demonstrating

that the company is similar to the other companies competing in the market, that is, it presents a leadership guided by rules and procedures, but also for the achievement of objectives and new challenges.

However, it still has some weaknesses and threats that need to be overcome, as well as the lack of recognition outside Spain and Portugal and also the lack of global presence compared to competing companies.

In short, we intend to highlight the importance that this work had in giving us knowledge of essential tools and concepts for our future, thus allowing the objectives initially proposed to be successfully achieved.

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